

Analysis and Computation of Extended Geometric Series and Summability

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Abstract: This paper analyses how the extended geometric series behaves on the computation of various parts of the series. This idea will enhance the knowledge of researchers working in sequence, series, summability and its applications.

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1. Analysis of Extended Geometric Series

In the earlier days, geometric series with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queuing theory, computer science and medicine [1]. An extended geometric series [2-7] is a geometric series with and without negative exponents.

Let's understand the summability of finite and infinite extended geometric series:

$$\sum_{f=-n}^n x^f = \sum_{h=-n}^{-3} x^h + x^{-2} + x^{-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} x^i + \sum_{j=k}^{n-2} x^j + x^{n-1} + x^n$$

Here, $x^{-2} + x^{-1} = \frac{x^{-1+1} - x^{-2}}{x-1} = \frac{x^2 - 1}{x^2(x-1)} = \frac{(x+1)(x-1)}{x^2(x-1)} = \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x^2}$ and

$$x^{n-1} + x^n = \frac{x^{n+1} - x^{n-1}}{x-1} = \frac{x^{n-1}(x^2 - 1)}{x-1} = \frac{x^{n-1}(x+1)(x-1)}{x-1} \quad \text{and}$$

$$x^{-(n-1)} + x^{-n} = \frac{x^{-n+2} - x^{-n}}{x-1} = \frac{(x^2 - 1)}{x^n(x-1)} = \frac{(x+1)(x-1)}{x^n(x-1)} = \frac{1}{x^{(n-1)}} + \frac{1}{x^n}$$

Also, $\sum_{i=-n}^{-1} x^i = \frac{x^{-1+1} - x^{-1}}{x-1} = \left(\frac{1 - \frac{1}{x^n}}{x-1} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x^i}$,

$$\sum_{i=2}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \left(\frac{1}{x-1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x^n} \right), \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x^i = \frac{1}{x-1},$$

$$\text{where } \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x^i = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^n x^i = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{1}{x^n}}{x - 1} \right) = \frac{1 - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{x^n}}{x - 1} = \frac{1}{x - 1} \left(\because \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{x^n} = 0 \right).$$

This is called summability of infinite geometric series.

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